

ABCD Analysis of Nanotechnology as Green Technology

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Abstract:

There are many analysis frameworks used to interpret concepts, ideas, technologies, models, systems, solutions to any problems, strategies, products or services of an organization, resources, etc. Out of them, recently developed analysis framework called ABCD analysis framework is flexible to use in both qualitative and quantitative manner. ABCD analysis method allows the researcher to interpret the given concepts, ideas, technologies, models, systems, solutions of any problems, strategies, products or services of an organization, resources including material, machine, men, money, and information, systematically by considering various determinant issues related to the problem under analysis. The various determinant issues like organizational issue, business issues, customer issues, technological issues, government issue, environmental issues, and societal issues are identified and the affecting factors under the constructs Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages are determined for identified key attributes. The critical constitutional elements of the nanotechnology as green technology are also identified for the same four constructs.

Keywords : ABCD Analysis Framework, Green Technology, Factor analysis, Elemental analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Technology analysis is a scientific, interactive, and communicative process that aims to contribute to the formation of public opinion on societal aspects of that technology. There are many analysis frameworks used to interpret concepts, ideas, technologies, models, systems,

solutions to any problems, strategies, products or services of an organization, resources, etc. Analysing a technology includes the study of development of that technology, its cost-benefits from the stakeholders point of view, its strength, weakness, opportunities and challenges (SWOC) [1--5], its advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages to the stakeholders (ABCD) [3, 6], its external analysis using political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal (PESTEL) framework [7-8], its performance analysis etc. Out of them, recently developed analysis framework called ABCD analysis framework is flexible to use in both qualitative and quantitative manner [3, 6, 9-12]]. ABCD analysis method allows the researcher to interpret the given concepts, ideas, technologies, models, systems, solutions of any problems, strategies, products or services of an organization, resources including material, machine, men, money, and information, systematically by considering various determinant issues related to the problem under analysis. The various determinant issues like organizational issue, product issue, customer issue, government issue, and environmental/ societal issues are identified and the affecting factors under the constructs Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages are determined for identified key attributes [5-6]. The ABCD analysing framework is also suitable for analysing a technology to study various affecting factors for different stakeholders including organization which adopted that technology for producing products through suitable processes under given constructs. In this paper, we have used ABCD analysing framework for the first time to analyse nanotechnology which is a general-purpose technology and also a green technology considered as a boon to the mankind due to its usefulness in solving all basic and advanced problems in the society to an optimum level which is very close to the ideal level.

2. FACTORS & ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS USING ABCD ANALYSIS

The ABCD analysis framework is developed based on two features which include (1) factor analysis and (2) elemental analysis. In factor analysis part, various affecting factors under each determinant issue of the technology are identified for each construct as per a chosen attribute. These affecting factors are identified using the Focus group method. The constructs used in factor analysis are (i) Advantages, (ii) Benefits, (iii) Constraints, (iv) Disadvantages. In the elemental analysis, the critical constitutional elements of the technology are also identified for same determinant issues under same four constructs (i) Advantages, (ii) Benefits, (iii) Constraints, (iv) Disadvantages (ABCD). The scores are given to each critical constituent element under all four constructs and based on calculating overall scores the importance of technology and its constructs in solving both basic and advanced problems in the organization/society are determined and rated [13-25]. In qualitative analysis model, only the affecting factors are determined under same four constructs which is also called ABCD listing [26-37].

3. NANOTECHNOLOGY AS GREEN TECHNOLOGY :

Green Technology (GT) can be used for environmental healing that reduces environmental damages created by the conventional industries in the society. It is expected that green technologies reduce the environmental degradation and supports to conserve natural resources. Green technologies are sustainable technologies which will not create a footprint when used for creating various products or processes. Green technologies support the use of natural organic materials and hence do not contribute to produce green gasses which are responsible for environmental degradation. Since green technologies do not support environmental degradation and creating the footprint, they are sustainable and contributes to improve the lifestyle and comfortability of the people.

The nanotechnology emerging as universal technology is expected to solve both basic needs and comfort wants of human beings. The basic needs include food, drinking water, energy, cloth, shelter, health and environment, and the comfort wants are space travel, expanded lifespan etc. Planned and controlled development in nanotechnology leads to environmental sustainability and hence can be used as green technology. Some of the applications of nanotechnology initially thought as green technology are [38] :

- Clean, secure, affordable, renewable energy;
- Stronger, lighter, more durable recyclable materials;
- Low-cost filters to provide clean drinking water from seawater and drainage;
- Medical devices and drugs to detect and treat diseases more effectively with fewer or no side effects;
- Lighting that uses a fraction of the energy associated with conventional systems;
- Sensors to detect and identify harmful chemical and biological agents;
- Techniques to clean up harmful chemicals in the environment.
- Green building and sustainable infrastructure.
- Modified production processes to minimize green gas emission.

The green Nanotechnology is evolved as a general-purpose technology due to its applications in all areas of society and now further growing as universal technology. Hence in the advanced form of universal technology, it will have a significant impact on almost all industries and all areas of society by offering better built, longer lasting, cleaner, safer, and smarter products for the home, for communications, for medicine, for transportation, for agriculture, and for the industry in general. Thus, by controlled utilization of nanotechnology for environmental sustainability, it can be developed as a green technology for sustainable society. Due to its capability of cleaning of the environmental footprint of other technologies, nanotechnology can be used to enhance the environmental-sustainability of processes currently producing negative externalities. Further nanotechnology can be used to produce various products which can have enhanced environmental sustainability.

Green nanotechnology has two objectives :

(1) The first objective is of producing [nanomaterials](#) and fabricating nanoproducts which do not harm the environment and human health and producing nano-products which contribute to solve the environmental problems. It uses many existing principles of [green science](#) and [green technology](#) to remove the toxic ingredients of nanomaterials and nano-products used in various industries of the society [39].

(2) The second objective of green nanotechnology involves developing nanoproducts that are used to clean the environment either directly or indirectly. In the direct method, nanomaterials or nanoproducts can be used to clean [hazardous waste](#) sites, [desalinate water](#), treatment of pollutants, or even sense and monitor any kind of environmental pollutants. In the indirect method, lightweight [nanocomposites](#) are used for fabricate automobile and spacecraft parts to save fuel and reduce materials used. Nanotechnology-enabled [fuel cells](#), [solar cells](#), and [light-emitting diodes](#) can reduce environmental pollution. Thus, nanotechnology can be used to green the environment for a long-time sustainability [39].

4. ABCD ANALYSIS OF NANOTECHNOLOGY :

The widespread growth of nanotechnology as green technology for various business processes can be analysed using many frameworks like SWOC, ABCD, and PESTLE. Out of them, ABCD framework is considered as most appropriate because, it uses many stakeholders as determinant issues. ABCD analysis framework is initially used to analyse systems, ideas, concepts, materials, strategies, and can be also used to analyse technology. Here, we are using ABCD framework to analyse nanotechnology as green technology by considering various determining issues like Organizational issues, Business issues, Consumers issues, Technological issues, Environmental issues, and Societal issues. Here, green technology features are considered as key attribute to identify the affecting factors under four constructs advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages.

5. FACTOR ANALYSIS OF NANOTECHNOLOGY

The affecting factors under each construct, for identified key attributes for a chosen issue are obtained using focus group method and listed in table 1. The analysis identified five determinant issues related to nanotechnology as green technology. These include organizational issues, business issues, customer issues, environmental issues, and societal issues. The key attributes identified under organizational issues includes employees of the organizations, infrastructure of the organizations, and the investment of the organizations which involved in nanotechnology based green business. Similarly, the business issues contain four key attributes including products, markets, expansion, and competitors. The

customers issues contain four key attributes including quality, features, cost, and support. The Environmental Issues contain two key attributes environmental degradation and Environmental Improvement. Finally, the societal issues contain three key attributes including basic problems, advanced problems, and immortality as given in table 3. Totally, in this analysis 64 affecting factors are identified and listed under the constructs advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages.

Table 1: Affecting factors of Nanotechnology as green technology under four constructs

Determinant Issues	Key Attributes	Advantages	Benefits	Constraints	Disadvantages
Organizational Issues	Employees	Skilled employees	Standard Quality	Difficulty in getting skilled employees	Cost of employees
	Infrastructure	Less infrastructure	Better return	New technology	Risk of new technology-based infrastructure investment
	Investment	New technology	High return	Higher investment	Risk for higher investment
Business Issues	Products	Nanoproducts can be green products	Clean environment	High production cost	May have hidden long term
	Markets	Easy due to special characteristics	Better business	Creating awareness	Initial Cost of creating awareness
	Competitors	Difficult to copy by competitors	Monopoly	New technology	Huge investment for research & development
	Expansion	Opportunity for expansion	Increased market share	Educating the collaborators	Copying by others
Consumer Issues	Quality	Optimum	Durability & renewable	Cost	May have side effects
	Features	Many	Comfortable life	Confused due to general purpose	Fear on Side effects

				technology	
	Cost	Low pollutant	Helpful for poor people	Affordability	Difficulty in large scale operation
	Support	Low failure rate	Low maintenance cost	Frequent service	Minimum service support
Environmental Issues	Environmental degradation	Less environmental degradation	Less pollution	Complexity in the system	Prolonged technology breakthrough than expected
	Environmental Improvement	Cleaning	Better environment	Scaling	Negative effects if any
Social Issues	Basic problems	Can be solved optimally	All basic problems will be solved	Commercialization	Delay in realization
	Advanced problems	Can be solved optimally	All advanced problems for human comfortability will be solved.	Still in experimental level	Unpredictable adverse effects
	Immortality	Life span expansion	Slow aging / No aging	Slow research in nanotechnology	Negative aspects of immortality /deathlessness

7. ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF NANOTECHNOLOGY :

Apart from affecting factors identified in previous section through factor analysis framework, one can also carryout the elemental analysis to identify critical constituent elements for each affecting factor for chosen determinant issues. These critical constituent elements for the four constructs advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages are listed in tables 2 to 5 respectively.

Table 2 : Advantages of Nanotechnology as Green technology

Particulars	Key Attributes	Factors Affecting	Critical Constituent Elements
			(i) Increased productivity

Organizational Issues	Employees	Skilled employees	(ii) Sophisticated facility (iii) More Jobs
	Infrastructure	Less infrastructure	(i) Small facilities (ii) Easy to manufacture (iii) Decreased cost
	Investment	New technology	(i) More initial investment (ii) New products (iii) New business
Business Issues	Products	Nanoproducts can be green products	(i) Low pollution (ii) Possibility to clean the environment (iii) Less side effects
	Marketing	Easy due to special characteristics	(i) Products have ideal characteristics (ii) Easy to market (iii) Many positive features
	Competitors	Difficult to copy by competitors	(i) Research for development (ii) Patented protection (iii) Uniqueness
	Expansion	Opportunity for expansion	(i) Global expansion opportunity (ii) Opportunity for cost leader (iii) Opportunity for collaboration
	Quality	Optimum	(i) Ideal products

Consumer Issues			(ii) Expected quality (iii) Durability
	Features	Many	(i) Green products (ii) Small & light in weight products (iii) Strong products
	Cost	Low pollutant	(i) Moderate cost-pollution ratio (ii) Controlling the pollution (iii) Low cost high durability
	Support	Low failure rate	(i) Durability (ii) No frequent replacement (iii) More operation period
Environmental Issues	Environmental degradation	Less environmental degradation	(i) No contribution to pollution (ii) Improving environment (iii) Quality environment for future generations
	Environmental Improvement	Cleaning of environment	(i) Possibility to clean environment (ii) Possibility to green the environment (iii) Improved products usage
Social Issues	Basic problems	Can be solves optimally	(i) Optimum to ideal solutions (ii) Opportunity to solve basic problems (iii)
	Advanced	Can be solved	(i) People can live comfortable

	problems	optimally	life (ii) Life is going to be easy (iii) Equality for everyone
	Immortality	Life span expansion	(i) Disease control (ii) Health equality (iii) Enhanced time for achievements

Table 3 : Benefits of Nanotechnology as Green technology

Particulars	Key Attributes	Factors Affecting	Critical Constituent Elements
Organizational Issues	Employees	Standard Quality	(i) Increased return (ii) Improved working conditions (iii) More salary
	Infrastructure	Better return	(i) Increased profit (ii) Sustainability (iii) Further investment opportunity
	Investment	High return	(i) More profit (ii) More return to stakeholders (iii) Expansion to other areas
Business Issues	Products	Clean environment	(i) Less pollution (ii) Good health (iii) Clean resources
	Marketing	Better business	(i) Business growth

			(ii) Attractive products (iii) More sales
	Competitors	Monopoly	(i) High tech products (ii) Patenting opportunity (iii) Enhanced earning
	Expansion	Increased market share	(i) More branches (ii) More subsidiaries (iii) More products for different problems
Consumer Issues	Quality	Durability & renewable	(i) No environmental pollution (ii) Clean products (iii) Trouble free operations
	Features	Comfortable life	(i) More essential features (ii) Need based support (iii) Availability of essential components
	Cost	Helpful for poor people	(i) Low cost (ii) Improved quality of life (iii) Abundantly available
	Support	Low maintenance cost	(i) Quality products (ii) Self-repairing technology (iii) Product replacement opportunity
Environmental	Environmental degradation	Less pollution	(i) Clean environment (ii) Green environment

Issues			(iii) Better living conditions
	Environmental Improvement	Better environment	(i) Comfortable life (ii) Health improvement (iii) Less diseases
Societal Issues	Basic problems	All basic problems will be solved	(i) Abundancy in food, water and energy (ii) Progressed civilization (iii) Improved living conditions
	Advanced problems	All advanced problems for human comfortability will be solved.	(i) Self sufficiency in Resources usage (ii) Decreased social differences (iii) Opportunities for everybody
	Immortality	Slow aging / No aging	(i) No diseases (ii) Automatic curing of diseases (iii) Expanded lifespan

Table 4 : Constraints of Nanotechnology as Green technology

Particulars	Key Attributes	Factors Affecting	Critical Constituent Elements
Organizational Issues	Employees	Difficulty in getting skilled employees	(i) Essential Technology education (ii) Continuous Research & training (iii) Advanced skills
	Infrastructure	New technology	(i) Investment for new technology infrastructure

			(ii) Continuous upgradation (iii) Frequent upgradation
	Investment	Higher investment	(i) Investment for survival (ii) Investment for sustainability (iii) Investment for monopoly
Business Issues	Products	High production cost	(i) Due to spreading of commercialization cost on production (ii) Due to complex technology (iii) Due to advanced features
	Marketing	Creating awareness	(i) Training to create awareness (ii) Acceptability of people (iii) Education level of people
	Competitors	New technology	(i) Enhanced competition due to new entrants (ii) Flood of resources initially due to high expectation (iii) Completion by existing business organizations
	Expansion	Educating the collaborators	(i) Importance and easiness of technology (ii) Product features (iii) Investment by collaborators
Consumer Issues	Quality	Cost	(i) Return on price (ii) Procrastination in usage (iii) Doubt on expected benefits

	Features	Confused due to general purpose technology	(i) Expected solutions in all areas of society (ii) Sustainability is a question (iii) Questions on side effects
	Cost	Affordability	(i) New technology is costly (ii) New technology is challenging (iii) New technology is difficult accept.
	Support	Frequent service	(i) New and hence less penetration (ii) Less service centres initially (iii) Services may be costly due to shortage of skilled people
Environmental Issues	Environmental degradation	Complexity of the system	(i) Controlling the emission of green gases is difficult process (ii) Monitoring and controlling the pollution is difficult (iii) Industrial environmental pollution is difficult to control
	Environmental Improvement	Scaling	(i) Large scale cleaning is difficult throughout the globe. (ii) Maintenance of cleaned environment is a challenge in terms of energy requirement (iii) All countries should involve in the process.
	Basic problems	Commercialization	(i) Commercialization of new technology is risky

Social Issues			(ii) Commercialization of new technology is difficult (iii) Commercialization of new technology is costly.
	Advanced problems	Still in experimental level	(i) Acceptance of new technology by people. (ii) Technology penetration is slow. (iii) Side effects are yet to know.
	Immortality	Slow research in nanotechnology	(i) Uncertainty in anticipated results (ii) Research laboratory results are difficult to commercialize in expected time frame (iii) Anticipated negative implications on immortality.

Table 5 : Disadvantages of Nanotechnology as Green technology

Particulars	Key Attributes	Factors Affecting	Critical Constituent Elements
Organizational Issues	Employees	Cost of employees	(i) Technically trained employees are costly. (ii) Increase in employee turnover. (iii) Employees have high bargain power.
	Infrastructure	Risk of new technology-based infrastructure	(i) Infrastructure investment risk

		investment	(ii) Infrastructure modification (iii) Uncertainty in infrastructure investment
	Investment	Risk for higher investment	(i) New technologies are slow penetrating (ii) People acceptance is difficult. (iii) Technologies which are initially promising may be prohibitively costly.
Business Issues	Products	May have hidden long term affects	(i) Side effects (ii) Fail to achieve goal (iii) Product features & promotions.
	Marketing	Initial Cost of creating awareness	(i) New brand building cost (ii) Challenge of creating awareness for new products. (iii) Challenge on product performance.
	Competitors	Huge investment for research & development	(i) Initial cost. (ii) Availing patent protection. (iii) Technology management
	Expansion	Copying by others	(i) Patent time (ii) Outsourcing (iii) Starting foreign subsidiaries
	Quality	May have side effects	(i) Minimizing side effects

Consumer Issues			(ii) Precautioning during use (iii) Quality control
	Features	Fear on side effects	(i) Check for branded products. (ii) Quality control through sufficient clinical trails (iii) Precaution during use.
	Cost	Difficulty in large scale operation	(i) Investment cost (ii) Maintenance cost (iii) Resource cost
	Support	Minimum service support	(i) After sales service (ii) Promised quality monitoring (iii) Feedback
Environmental Issues	Environmental degradation	Prolonged technology breakthrough time than expected	(i) Waiting for breakthrough (ii) Govt. involvement (iii) Stringent rules
	Environmental Improvement	Negative effects if any	(i) Environmental side effects (ii) Cost of environmental improvement (iii) Disputes in countries responsibilities
Social Issues	Basic problems	Delay in realization	(i) Long time problems are difficult to tackle. (ii) Delay in patent acceptance (iii) Delay in availing finance for investments

	Advanced problems	Unpredictable adverse effects	(i) Fear in adopting new technology (ii) Some times predictions may not work. (iii) Global regulations may hinder firms performance.
	Immortality	Negative aspects of immortality /deathlessness	(i) Aging (ii) Antiaging (iii) Stagnated growth & challenges.

8. CONCLUSION :

In this paper, we have analysed the Nanotechnology as green technology using ABCD analysis framework. 64 affecting factors of nanotechnology as green technology and 192 critical constituent elements are identified in the analysis under the four constructs advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages. Thus, nanotechnology as a technology for sustaining and improving green environment has many opportunities and challenges to solve organizational problems, business problems, customers problems, environmental problems, and societal problems in order to change the life style and health of the human beings and hence considered as boon of human species to grow, expand, and enjoy the life without may varies in future days. Such interpretation of nanotechnology as a green technology through its affecting factors and critical constituent elements are going to interpret the consequences of this new technology favourable continuation of human life in this universe.

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